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Stolen Car Detection Using Image Processing

BY

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ABSTRACT

The strategy of the project was to design automatic system for Detecting stolen cars without mounting any signal transmitter on the car. Thus, the project was to investigate and construct an application whereby the system would recognize the vehicle license plate at a check post or at gate entrance of the parking lot. The system would be based on a personal computer and software packages available, MATLAB program and a digital camera, which help to capture the images of the vehicle license plate and a laser sensor to detect the presence of the car. A research would be conducted and developed a system that would be able to extract the vehicle license plate number. Next,an algorithm would also be designed which identifies the vehicle license plate for the purpose of recognition.

The general algorithm involves the following steps:

- Image Processing: The image captured is preprocessed for faster processing.
- Plate localization and extraction: To obtain the vehicle plate sub image.
- Character Segmentation/Recognition: Resample and threshold in order to isolate the license plate character from vehicle license plate. We used neural network for recognition of vehicle license plate character. The neural Network would be trained off-line with the characters and numbers.
- Evaluating the performance of the algorithm and compare the performance with other reported work.
- Implementing a file management system or database for storing the images of vehicle license plate, numbers and characters.

PREFACE

Image processing is any form of signal processing for which the input is an image (Signal), such as a photograph or video frame, the output of image processing may be either an image or, a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image. Most image-processing techniques involve treating the image as a two-dimensional signal and applying standard signal-processing techniques.

Terrorism is the biggest problem here in Pakistan. The main cause of this problem is lack of security or weak security systems. In Pakistan, people Snatches or stole cars and do crime using that stolen vehicle so that they cannot get busted. There was this day when we saw news that a car in Peshawar blasts and so many people got injured and killed. That sure was a stolen car. We can track out such cars using the project mentioned in this report.

In this project we are going to detect number of car using simple camera. We can put the camera at the check posts on high ways to see how many illegal cars are going through the high way. By using image processing we will get the number of car. We will then match it with list of the numbers of wanted cars. If the car is found illegal, a signal is generated to inform the security personals in that area. The application of our project is also very useful for prohibited areas like military areas or civil colonies where many vehicles are in and out in a day.

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Contents

	Page
Chapter#01 Introduction	7-11
1.1 Introduction to our Project	
1.2 Project Background	
1.3 Basic description of Project	
1.4 Objective	
1.5 Applications	
1.6 Limitations	
Chapter#02 Project Design	12-22
2.1 Block Diagram	
2.2 Flow Chart	
2.3 Image Processing	
2.4 Software	
2.5 Hardware Components	

Chapter#03 Methodology of Project **23-45**

3.1 Image Acquisition

3.2 Image Pre-Processing

3.3 Character Recognition

3.4 Database Comparison

3.5 Results

Chapter#04 Source Code **46-72**

4.1 Program

4.2 Algorithm

Chapter#05 SCDS **73-82**

5.1 Future Extensions

5.2 Database

5.3 Conclusions

5.4 References

Chapter # 01

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction To Our Project

With the growth in the population and needs of human beings, the use of vehicles has been increasing from the last few decades. This increasing number of vehicles needs to be controlled from the point of view of security and management. However, controlling a huge amount of traffic is a big problem which needs to be solved. Automatic vehicle detection and recognition can solve this problem. For that the rapid technological development in the field of image processing can be used. One solution can be the extraction and recognition of vehicle's license plate from a digital image. Automatic vehicle plate detection and recognition is a key technique in most of traffic related applications such as searching for a stolen car, road traffic monitoring, and automatic parking lots access control.

1.2 Project Background

From the last few decades, Vehicle License Plate Recognition (VLPR) is the quite popular and active research topic in image processing domain. With constantly increasing traffic on roads, there is a need of intelligent traffic management systems which not only detect and track a vehicle but also identify it. Terrorism is the biggest problem here in Pakistan. The main cause of this problem is lack of security or weak security systems. In Pakistan, people snatches or stole vehicles and do crime using these stolen vehicles so that they cannot get busted. We can track out such vehicles using this project. Stolen car detection using License Plate Recognition is an Image Processing System whereby it is used to recognize the vehicles by identifying the license plate. It is basically use for traffic and security purposes.

1.3 Basic Description Of Project

Firstly, the vehicle would stop at the car gantry. The cycle would start when the vehicle steps over the detector or sensors.

Secondly, camera would be activated and images of the front picture of the vehicle would be taken. The system would read the information pixels of the vehicle and run the recognition process.

Thirdly, the system would apply certain algorithm to analyze the vehicle image. Besides analyzing, the images would be enhance, locating the vehicle plate position and extract the characters from the vehicle plate. Next, the characters would be recognized.

Lastly, the system would try to match the recognized vehicle plate number with the car plate database. Result would be transferred to the next check post or highway police as shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1

1.4 Objective

The overall objective of the project is to develop a system to recognize vehicle license plate from a car at a gate entrance of a parking lot. The software could lead to a cheaper and faster way of enhancing and determined the performance of the recognition system. The system will be based on a Personal Computer such that it will generate report on the vehicle license plate it has captured. Once the vehicle license plate is captured, the characters will be recognized and displayed. Besides, the system can also serve as a security purpose whereby it can spot on any wanted or stolen vehicles.

1.5 Applications

There are several applications where automatic license plate recognition can be used.

- Enhanced vehicle theft prevention.
- Building a comprehensive database of traffic movement.
- Security monitoring of roads, checkpoints, etc.
- Military areas security.
- Recognition of vehicles in civil colonies.

1.6 Limitations

Due to limited time that we possess and dealing with image vision software, it is not advisable to include all of the possible cases. Thus, we have to set a list of limitations to make the project more systematic and manageable. The limitations are listed as below:

- Image taken only when vehicle is stationary.
- Captured image of vehicle at fixed distance.
- Captured image of vehicle at fixed angle.
- There will be no motion capture image.
- Take only the front view image of the car.
- Vehicle with only yellow color number plate is detected.

Chapter # 02

PROJECT DESIGN

2.1 Block Diagram

2.2 Flow Chart

2.3 Image Processing

Image processing is any form of signal processing for which the input is an image(Signal), such as a photograph or video frame, the output of image processing may be either an image or, a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image. Most image-processing techniques involve treating the image as a two-dimensional signal and applying standard signal-processing techniques. An image is an array, or a matrix, of square pixels (picture elements) arranged in columns and rows. In this project various image processing techniques are used to extract the number of vehicles and compare the number with stolen vehicle database.

An image — an array or a matrix of pixels arranged in columns and rows shown in this figure.

2.4 Software

MATLAB software is used for image processing on vehicle images. When working with images in **MATLAB**, there are many things to keep in mind such as loading an image, using the right format, saving the data as different data types, how to display an image, conversion between different image formats, etc. **MATLAB** is used for image processing because processing is very faster in **MATLAB** and it is friendly user software.

The following image formats are supported by **MATLAB**:

- BMP
- GIF
- HDF
- JPEG
- JPG
- JP2
- PBM
- PCX
- TIFF
- XWD
- Etc

2.5 Hardware Components

2.5.1 Camera

2.5.2 Laser Sensor

2.5.3 Serial Port

2.5.4 Personal Computer

2.5.1 Camera (A4 Tech PK-750G Anti-glare Webcam)

- Anti-glare coating- Avoids reflections and generates vivid images in perfect color.
- Superior low-light performance.
- Provides the best image quality in low-light conditions.
- Intelligent multisampling.
- Delivers fluent video transmission with no aliasing and no lag.
- Still image resolution up to 16 Megapixel by software interpolated.

2.5.2 Laser Sensor

The receiver is based on the MAX232A IC for receiving RS-232 compatible voltage signals. The receiving sensor is a Light emitting diode (LDR). Although the laser wavelength is in the visible spectrum (~670nm) the LDR response band (550nm to 1050nm) is wide enough to sense the intense laser beam. The signal from the LDR is buffered via a pair of Schmitt trigger buffers to clean up and square the signal. The output of the second buffer is then directly converted to a RS-232 standard signal via the MAX232A.

The MAX232A generates +10V and -10V voltage swings using a dual charge-pump voltage converter from a single +5VDC rail. Several different versions of the MAX232 chip exist. The A version requires only 0.1 uF capacitors for the charge-pump and inverter, whereas the MAX232 requires 1uF capacitors. The advantage of the A version is that it has faster response times, and allows for faster data rates.

RS-232 Light Sensor

2.5.2.1 Max232

Description

The MAX232 is a dual driver/receiver that includes a capacitive voltage generator to supply TIA/EIA-232-F voltage levels from a single 5-V supply. Each receiver converts TIA/EIA-232-F inputs to 5-V TTL/CMOS levels. These receivers have a typical threshold of 1.3 V, a typical hysteresis of 0.5 V, and can accept ± 30 -V inputs. Each driver converts TTL/CMOS input levels into TIA/EIA-232-F levels. The driver, receiver, and voltage-generator functions are available as cells in the Texas Instruments LinASIC library.

ORDERING INFORMATION

T_A	PACKAGE†		ORDERABLE PART NUMBER	TOP-SIDE MARKING
0°C to 70°C	PDIP (N)	Tube of 25	MAX232N	MAX232N
	SOIC (D)	Tube of 40	MAX232D	MAX232
		Reel of 2500	MAX232DR	
	SOIC (DW)	Tube of 40	MAX232DW	MAX232
		Reel of 2000	MAX232DWR	
SOP (NS)	Reel of 2000	MAX232NSR	MAX232	
-40°C to 85°C	PDIP (N)	Tube of 25	MAX232IN	MAX232IN
	SOIC (D)	Tube of 40	MAX232ID	MAX232I
		Reel of 2500	MAX232IDR	
	SOIC (DW)	Tube of 40	MAX232IDW	MAX232I
		Reel of 2000	MAX232IDWR	

† Package drawings, standard packing quantities, thermal data, symbolization, and PCB design guidelines are available at www.ti.com/sc/package.

Schematic

2.5.2.2 Hex Inverter with Schmitt Triggers

Description

The general logical performance of these INVERTER gates resembles that of the 7402 or other typical INVERTERS. The addition of the Schmitt Triggered circuitry affects the wave forms that are produced as an output. Schmitt Trigger Circuits are generally constructed from a comparator, but instead of the usual negative feedback, they implement a positive feedback mechanism.

2.5.2.3 Voltage Regulator

Description

7805 is a **voltage regulator** integrated circuit. It is a member of 78xx series of fixed linear voltage regulator ICs. The voltage source in a circuit may have fluctuations and would not give the fixed voltage output. The **voltage regulator IC** maintains the output voltage at a constant value. The xx in 78xx indicates the fixed output voltage it is designed to provide. 7805 provides +5V regulated power supply. Capacitors of suitable values can be connected at input and output pins depending upon the respective voltage levels.

Pin Description

Pin No	Function	Name
1	Input voltage (5V-18V)	Input
2	Ground (0V)	Ground
3	Regulated output; 5V (4.8V-5.2V)	Output

Schematic

2.5.2.4 Light Dependent Resistor

When the light level is low the resistance of the LDR is high. This prevents current from flowing to the base of the transistors. Consequently the LED does not light.

However, when light shines onto the LDR its resistance falls and current flows into the base of the first transistor and then the second transistor. The LED lights.

Structure

2.5.3 Serial Port

In computing, a **serial port** is a serial communication physical interface through which information transfers in or out one bit at a time. Modern computers without serial ports may require serial-to-USB converters to allow compatibility with RS 232 serial devices. Serial ports are still used in applications such as industrial automation systems, scientific instruments, shop till systems and some industrial and consumer products. Server computers may use a serial port as a control console for diagnostics. Network equipment (such as routers and switches) often use serial console for configuration. Serial ports are still used in these areas as they are simple, cheap and their console functions are highly standardized and widespread. A serial port requires very little supporting software from the host system. In this project serial port would be used to send the output of laser sensor as input to the computer to start the algorithm on **MATLAB** Software.

Serial Port Pin Configuration

2.5.4 Personal Computer

Personal computer with high configuration or laptop would be used to make the algorithm for image processing of vehicle images to detect the number on MATLAB software. Computer would also be used for serial port communication of laser sensor to start the algorithm on MATLAB software.

Chapter # 03

METHODOLOGY OF PROJECT

3.1 Image Acquisition

Image acquisition is the first phase in car license plate recognition process. Image can be acquired either by using an analog camera with a scanner or by using a digital camera. Image acquisition through analog camera is impractical. The reliable and practical approach is acquiring images through digital camera. The video camera can also be used. The system performance can be improved by using a frame grabber, which will grab a single frame, with the camera in real time applications. In this project digital images were used, which were taken from a digital camera for image acquisition phase. Only the pictures taken from the front side of the car were included in the dataset.

A video object is constructed using “videoinput” command

```
obj = videoinput(adaptorname)
```

the video would be viewed by the following operation

```
preview(obj);
```

A delay of three seconds is introduced in the program so that the camera could get a clearer view.

```
Pause(3)
```

A frame from the video is then extracted as an image for further processing

```
frame = getsnapshot(obj);
```

```
image(frame);
```

Video preview is then close using:

```
closepreview(obj)
```


Snapshot of Object

3.2 Image Preprocessing

3.2.1 Number Plate Detection

3.2.2 Grayscale of Image

3.2.3 Gray Thresh

3.2.4 Binary Image

3.2.5 Complement of Image

3.2.6 Image Dilation

3.2.7 Area of Image

3.2.8 Label of Image

3.2.9 Clear Border of Image

3.2.10 Area Open of Image

3.2.11 Image Crop

3.2.1 Number Plate Detection

For number plate extraction color based approach was used in this project. Only yellow color plates were extracted by the algorithm, if more colors number plates are wanted then algorithm would be changed. By using this technique it was easy to extract the number plate of a vehicle. For example if color of plate is yellow then yellow color would be detected by the image of the vehicle and number plate would be extracted by image processing.

$Car = (single(R) + single(G))/2 - single(B);$

$Car = Car > 50;$

By using this formula yellow color was detected and number plate was extracted.

3.2.2 Grayscale of Image

A grayscale image (also called gray-scale, gray scale, or gray-level) is a data matrix whose values represent intensities within some range. MATLAB stores a grayscale image as an individual matrix, with each element of the matrix corresponding to one image pixel. By convention, this documentation uses the variable name `I` to refer to grayscale images. The matrix can be of class `uint8`, `uint16`, `int16`, `single`, or `double`. While grayscale images are rarely saved with a color map, MATLAB uses a color map to display them. For a matrix of class `single` or `double`, using the default grayscale color map, the intensity 0 represents black and the intensity 1 represents white. For a matrix of type `uint8`, `uint16`, or `int16`, the intensity `int min(class (I))` represents black and the intensity `intmax(class (I))` represents white. Command used for grayscale image is

```
licenseplateA = rgb2gray(Licenseplate1)
```


3.2.3 Gray Thresh

Global image threshold using Otsu's method

Syntax:

`level = graythresh(I)`

`level = graythresh(I)` computes a global threshold (`level`) that can be used to convert an intensity image to a binary image with `im2bw`. `level` is a normalized intensity value that lies in the range `[0, 1]`. The `graythresh` function uses Otsu's method, which chooses the threshold to minimize the intraclass variance of the black and white pixels. Multidimensional arrays are converted automatically to 2-D arrays using `reshape`. The `graythresh` function ignores any nonzero imaginary part of `I`.

$\sigma^{2B} = \omega_0(\mu_0 - \mu_T)^2 + \omega_1(\mu_1 - \mu_T)^2$; where

$$\omega_0 = \sum_{q=0}^{k-1} P_q(r_q),$$

$$\omega_1 = \sum_{q=k}^{L-1} P_q(r_q)$$

$$\mu_0 = \sum_{q=0}^{k-1} qP_q(r_q) / \omega_0$$

$$\mu_1 = \sum_{q=k}^{L-1} qP_q(r_q) / \omega_1$$

$$\mu_T = \sum_{q=0}^{L-1} qP_q(r_q)$$

3.2.4 Binary Image

Convert image to binary image, based on threshold

Syntax:

`BW = im2bw(I, level)`

`BW = im2bw(I, level)` converts the grayscale image `I` to a binary image. The output image `BW` replaces all pixels in the input image with luminance greater than `level` with the value 1 (white) and replaces all other pixels with the value 0 (black). Specify `level` in the range `[0,1]`. This range is relative to the signal levels possible for the image's class. Therefore, a `level` value of 0.5 is midway between black and white, regardless of class. To compute the `level` argument, you can use the function `graythresh`. If you do not specify `level`, `im2bw` uses the value 0.5.

If the input image is not a grayscale image, `im2bw` converts the input image to grayscale, and then converts this grayscale image to binary by thresholding.

3.2.5 Complement of Image

Complement image

Syntax:

```
IM2 = imcomplement(IM)
```

`IM2 = imcomplement(IM)` computes the complement of the image `IM`. `IM` can be a binary, grayscale, or RGB image. `IM2` has the same class and size as `IM`. In the complement of a binary image, zeros become ones and ones become zeros; black and white are reversed. In the complement of an intensity or RGB image, each pixel value is subtracted from the maximum pixel value supported by the class (or 1.0 for double-precision images) and the difference is used as the pixel value in the output image. In the output image, dark areas become lighter and light areas become darker.

3.2.6 Image Dilation

Dilate image

Syntax:

```
IM2 = imdilate(IM,SE)
```

`IM2 = imdilate(IM,SE)` dilates the grayscale, binary, or packed binary image `IM`, returning the dilated image, `IM2`. The argument `SE` is a structuring element object, or array of structuring element objects, returned by the `strel` function.

If `IM` is logical and the structuring element is flat, `imdilate` performs binary dilation; otherwise, it performs grayscale dilation. If `SE` is an array of structuring element objects, `imdilate` performs multiple dilations of the input image, using each structuring element in `SE` in succession.

3.2.7 Area of Image

Area of objects in binary image

Syntax

```
total = bwarea(BW)
```

`total = bwarea(BW)` estimates the area of the objects in binary image `BW`. `total` is a scalar whose value corresponds roughly to the total number of on pixels in the image, but might not be exactly the same because different patterns of pixels are weighted differently.

3.2.8 Label of Image

Label connected components in 2-D binary image

Syntax:

`L = bwlabel(BW, n)`

`[L, num] = bwlabel(BW, n)`

`L = bwlabel(BW, n)` returns a matrix `L`, of the same size as `BW`, containing labels for the connected objects in `BW`. The variable `n` can have a value of either 4 or 8, where 4 specifies 4-connected objects and 8 specifies 8-connected objects. If the argument is omitted, it defaults to 8.

The elements of `L` are integer values greater than or equal to 0. The pixels labeled 0 are the background. The pixels labeled 1 make up one object; the pixels labeled 2 make up a second object; and so on.

`[L, num] = bwlabel(BW, n)` returns in `num` the number of connected objects found in `BW`.

3.2.9 Clear Border of Image

Suppress light structures connected to image border.

Syntax:

```
IM2 = imclearborder(IM)
```

```
IM2 = imclearborder(IM,conn)
```

`IM2 = imclearborder(IM)` suppresses structures that are lighter than their surroundings and that are connected to the image border. (In other words, use this function to clear the image border.) `IM` can be a grayscale or binary image. The output image, `IM2`, is grayscale or binary, respectively. The default connectivity is 8 for two dimensions, 26 for three dimensions, and `conndef(ndims(BW),'maximal')` for higher dimensions.

`IM2 = imclearborder(IM,conn)` specifies the desired connectivity.

3.2.10 Area Open of Image

Morphologically open binary image (remove small objects)

Syntax:

```
BW2 = bwareaopen(BW, P)
```

```
BW2 = bwareaopen(BW, P, conn)
```

`BW2 = bwareaopen(BW, P)` removes from a binary image all connected components (objects) that have fewer than `P` pixels, producing another binary image, `BW2`. The default connectivity is 8 for two dimensions, 26 for three dimensions, and `conndef(ndims(BW), 'maximal')` for higher dimensions.

`BW2 = bwareaopen(BW, P, conn)` specifies the desired connectivity.

3.2.11 Image Crop

Crop image

Syntax:

`I2 = imcrop(I, rect)` crops the image `I`. `rect` is a four-element position vector [`xmin` `ymin` `width` `height`] that specifies the size and position of the crop rectangle.

imresize

Resize image

Syntax:

`B = imresize(A, [mrowsncols])`

`B = imresize(A, [mrowsncols])` returns image `B` that has the number of rows and columns specified by `[mrowsncols]`. Either `NUMROWS` or `NUMCOLS` may be `NaN`, in which case `imresize` computes the number of rows or columns automatically to preserve the image aspect ratio.

3.3 Character Recognition

A network is to be designed and trained to recognize the 26 letters of the alphabet and 0-9 numbers.

corr2

2-D correlation coefficient

Syntax:

```
r = corr2(A,B)
```

`r = corr2(A,B)` computes the correlation coefficient between A and B, where A and B are matrices or vectors of the same size.

A and B can be numeric or logical. The return value r is a scalar double.

Example:

Compute the correlation coefficient between an image and the same image processed with a median filter.

```
I = imread('pout.tif');
```

```
J = medfilt2(I);
```

```
R = corr2(I,J)
```

```
R = 0.9959
```

Algorithm:

corr2 computes the correlation coefficient using

$$r = \frac{\sum_m \sum_n (A_{mn} - \bar{A})(B_{mn} - \bar{B})}{\sqrt{\left(\sum_m \sum_n (A_{mn} - \bar{A})^2 \right) \left(\sum_m \sum_n (B_{mn} - \bar{B})^2 \right)}}$$

corr2 computes the correlation coefficient using

Where $\bar{A} = \text{mean2}(A)$, and $\bar{B} = \text{mean2}(B)$.

Templates for character Recognition:

0 1 2 3 4 5

6 7 8 9

A B C D E F

G H I J K L

M N O P Q R

S T U V W X

Y Z

Extracted Number

The number would be extracted from the image of the car and the extraction is successful and the message box shows the extracted number.

Extracted Number: ARF144

3.4 Database Comparison

The data base of stolen car numbers would be created. The extracted numbers of the cars that would be stopped at check posts on highways would be compared with the stolen car numbers that were mentioned in database. If the extracted number would be matched with the any of the stolen car number in database than the stolen car would be detected and if the extracted number would not be matched with any stolen car number in database then the car would be cleared. Following is the algorithm used for importing the database in **MATLAB**.

****Database Load****

```
% ImPOrtingVariaBlesFrOMfiLEs
newData1 = importdata('Book1.xlsx')
vars = fieldnames(newData1);
for i = 1:length(vars)
    assignin('base', vars{i}, newData1.(vars{i}));
end
```

Following are the stolen car numbers selected for database. Each of these numbers would be compared with the extracted number.

Car1	ARF144
Car2	CN9919
Car3	AJL256
Car4	AJM109
Car5	AKA892
Car6	AWS108

3.5 Results

A message box would show the result of database comparison. If the extracted number would be matched with the any of the stolen car number in database than the message box would show that the stolen car would be detected and if the extracted number would not be matched with any stolen car number in database then the message box would show that the car would be cleared.

```
msgbox(sprintf('StolEnCaRdetEctEd...!! \n \n \" %s \" .\n',word),'Extraction Success');
```

```
else
```

```
msgbox(sprintf('CaRclEArED...!! \n \n %s \n.',word),'Extraction Success');
```

```
end
```

Also this message would be sent to highway police to alert the police. The message would be sent from **MATLAB**.

For example:

```
myaddress = 'muneebahmed882@gmail.com';
mypassword = '*****';

setpref('Internet','E_mail',myaddress);
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Server','smtp.gmail.com');
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Username',myaddress);
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Password',mypassword);

props = java.lang.System.getProperties;
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.auth','true');
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.class', ...
'javax.net.ssl.SSLSocketFactory');
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.port','465');

sendmail(myaddress, 'Alert message', '%s This car is stolen.',word);
```


Alert Message on Mobile Phone

Chapter # 04

SCDS

(STOLEN CAR DETECTION SYSTEM)

4.1 Future Extensions

Following are the future extensions for above the mentioned project:

- Metal detector could be used in place of laser sensor.
- Algorithm could be improved for number plates other than yellow color.
- Algorithm could be improved for different font styles of number plates.
- The project could be implemented on traffic signals for monitoring of traffic flow.
- Message could be sent through GSM module directly to the police servers.
- This project could be modified for other vehicles such as bikes and Rickshaws.

4.2 Problems

The Approaches that failed for this project are as follows:

- **Taking ratio of images for character recognition.**

Formula used for character recognition that failed due to very low efficiency is:

```
X=bwareaopen(A)
```

```
Y=bwperim(A,4)
```

```
Y=sum(Y(:))
```

```
Y=Y^2
```

```
ratio=X/Y;
```

Since it calculates the area then divide it by the square of sum of perimeter of the image. It was a success with object detection but fails for character segmentation.

- **Threshold of image**

It is one of the main problems we faced in our project. Threshold is main characteristic of an image. It changes with the contrast. We were using this in our first approach for the detection of car plate.

Threshold is calculated using:

$$X = \text{graythresh}(A)$$

4.3 Database

Following are few of the cars from our database which we used for our project:

4.4 Conclusion

A lot of research has been performed on detection and recognition of license plate. Different researchers provided different methods and techniques for this process. However, every technique has its own advantages and disadvantages.

Furthermore each country has its own License plate numbering system, colors, language of characters, style (font) and sizes. Even within the same country the license plate differs from state to state and in terms of types of License plate. Moreover, there are different countries which have not yet used the concept of automatic License plate

detection and recognition. Although significant research is carried out for English, Chinese, French car plate detection and recognition. However, desirable work for Pakistani license plate detection and recognition do not get required attention in the literature. It is mainly due to the reason of different style of Pakistani license plates. Although some research have been performed on Pakistani LP detection and recognition, and have been implemented. This project is different from the previous work because it is actually working without any human being's presence on the site.

Before the detection and recognition process started, first of a laser sensor connected to the algorithm detects the presence of car. Which then signals to the camera to take the image for further processing? When the image is taken it is forwarded to the pre-processing block of the detection. A formula to extract the yellow color is used (mentioned in the algorithm above) to extract yellow colors. Since yellow is the

standard color for cars number plate in Sindh, Pakistan. The detected objects were divided into “Plate” and “not Plate” categories automatically using a loop. After the plate is localized and extracted, it moves to the character segmentation block of the program. There the characters are being segmented in the character segmentation phase. Which then moves to character recognition part. Characters are being stored in an array as the cars numbers. That array is then matched to the numbers stored in the database as stolen cars. If the car is found stolen a message is generated and sends to the mobile phone with cars number.

Car Plate:

Analysis Table:

S.No	Picture	Detected Targets	Plates Detected	Worng Detection	Result %
1.	Image1	3	1	0	100
2.	Image2	1	1	0	100
3.	Image3	5	1	0	100
4.	Image4*	2	0	0	0
5.	Image5	1	1	0	100
				Mean	80%

* Due to greater area of plate size, None of the object was selected as car plate

Characters:

Analysis Table:

S.No	Picture	Characters Detected	Worng Detection	Result %
1.	Image1	6	0	100
2.	Image2	6	0	100
3.	Image3	5	0	100
4.	Image4*	0	0	0
5.	Image5	6	0	100
			Mean	80%

* Since the plate was not detected that is why no characters were found

4.5 References

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- Sir Rana Javed
- Sir Faisal (N.E.D)
- Sir Haris Zikrur Rehman
- Sir Fauzan Saeed
- Sir Shiraz Latif
- Sir Salman Mobin
- Mam Adiba Jaffar
- Mam Anum Bashir
- Sir Waseem Zeeshan
- Sir Atif Fareed

4.6 Appendix

Appendix A

Program:

In this algorithm an infinite loop would be run consisting of our algorithm.

While 1

End

Serial port “COM1” would be connected using command “serial”. Following Parameters of serial port would be set using “set” command.

- BaudRate', 9600
- 'DataBits', 8
- 'Parity', 'none'
- 'StopBits', 1,

Another nested infinite loop would execute that will take input through the serial port of the laser sensor continuously.

When a positive signal is received the loop would be terminated using “break” command.

```
If out==1
```

```
Break;
```

That leads the execution to the program to video acquisition part of the algorithm.

Which would connect the camera to the the MATLAB.

A video object is constructed using “videoinput” command

```
obj = videoinput(adaptorname)
```

the video would be viewed by the following operation

```
preview(obj);
```

A delay of three seconds is introduced in the program so that the camera could get a clearer view.

```
Pause(3)
```

A frame from the video is then extracted as an image for further processing

```
frame = getsnapshot(obj);
```

```
image(frame);
```

Video preview is then close using:

```
closepreview(obj)
```

The image from the camera is then goes into the preprocessing part of the program.

First, its red, blue and green frames would be extracted.

Using:

```
R=image(:,:,1)
```

```
G=image(:,:,2)
```

```
B=image(:,:,3)
```

The following formula would then be applied to extract the yellow color from the image as white and the remaining as black.

```
Car = (single(R) + single(G))/2 - single(B);
```

```
Car = Car > 50;
```

Using the following command the border of the image is being removed:

```
X=imclearborder(A,conn)
```

Further, small objects would be removed using:

```
X=bwareaopen(A,1000)
```

Now, using “bwlabel” number of objects in the image would be calculated.

```
[Labels,NumberOfObjects] = bwlabel(A,8);
```

A loop to calculate area of each object is executed

```
for loop = 1:1:NOD1
TT1(loop) = bwarea(find(Label1==loop));
end
```

Another loop would be run that will extract all the objects from the image.

```
for loop = 1:1:NOD1
[R,C] = find(Label1==loop);
%offset = 0;
Rmin = min(R) %- offset;
Rmax = max(R) %+ offset;
Cmin = min(C) %- offset;
Cmax = max(C) %+ offset;
Carplate{loop} = imcrop(Car1,[CminRmin (Cmax-Cmin),(Rmax - Rmin)]);
%figure, imshow(Carplate{loop});
end
```

Another loop is executed after that to check the extracted object as number plate by checking its matrix size.

```
for loop = 1:1:NOD1
    a=size(Carplate{loop});
    if a<[50 100 4]
        Bulleyes=1;
        Carplate1=Carplate{loop};
```

```
break;
```

```
else
```

```
Bulleyes=0;
```

```
end
```

```
end
```

Now the extracted number plate would be change to gray scale and then into binary image.

```
X=rgb2gray(A)
```

```
BW=im2bw(X)
```

Complement of it would be taken

```
X=imcomplement(BW)
```

Then again the border is being cleared and small objects would be removed using:

```
X=imclearborder(A,conn)
```

```
X=bwareaopen(X,15)
```

Again number of objected would be calculated and extracted. And extracted character would be resized to a [42 24] matrix using:

```
for loop = 1:1:NOD2
```

```
[R,C] = find(labels2==loop);
```

```
offset = 0;
```

```
Rmin = min(R) - offset;
```

```
Rmax = max(R) + offset;
```

```
Cmin = min(C) - offset;
```

```
Cmax = max(C) + offset;
```

```
Numbers {loop} = imcrop(CarplateAO,[CminRmin (Cmax-Cmin),(Rmax - Rmin)]);
```

```
%figure, imshow(Numbers {loop})
```

```
NNumbers1 {loop}=imresize(Numbers {loop}, [42 24]);
```

```
NNumbers1 {loop} =~ NNumbers1 {loop};
```

```
%figure, imshow(NNumbers1 {loop});end
```

Then comes the recognition part of the program. Each extracted character would be matched with the images of numbers (0-9) and letters (A-Z). Using the function “corr2” in a loop.

```
sem=corr2(templates {1,n},imagn);
```

then the recognized group of characters i.e. the car number is matched with those that are in the database using:

```
s=isequal(word,a);
```

If the number is found or matched with the database (Stolen cars number) a message would be sent to a cell phone using:

```
myaddress = 'muneebahmed882@gmail.com';
```

```
mypassword = '*****';
```

```
setpref('Internet','E_mail',myaddress);
```

```
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Server','smtp.gmail.com');  
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Username',myaddress);  
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Password',mypassword);  
  
props = java.lang.System.getProperties();  
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.auth','true');  
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.class', ...  
'javax.net.ssl.SSLSocketFactory');  
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.port','465');  
sendmail(myaddress, 'Alert message', '%s This car is stolen.',word);
```

And a message would be generated on the screen by:

```
msgbox(sprintf('StolEnCaRdetEctEd..!! \n \n \" %s \" \n',word),'Extraction Success');  
msgbox(sprintf('CaRclEArED..!! \n \n %s \n',word),'Extraction Success');
```

Appendix B

Algorithm:

****Program Start****

```
while 1
```

```
% DeleTingVarIAbLES
```

```
clear
```

```
% CleARiNGScreEN
```

```
clc
```

****Database Load****

```
% ImPORtingVariaBlesFrOMfiLEs
```

```
newData1 = importdata('Book1.xlsx')
```

```
vars = fieldnames(newData1);
```

```
for i = 1:length(vars)
```

```
    assignin('base', vars{i}, newData1.(vars{i}));
```

```
end
```

****Laser Sensor****

```
% SenSorInpUT
```

```
% DecLAriNgObJECt S FoR COM POrt
```

```
S = serial('COM1');
```

```
% SettInGs
```

```
set(S,'BaudRate', 9600, 'DataBits', 8, 'Parity', 'none','StopBits', 1, 'FlowControl', 'none');
```

```
% OpeNPORT
```

```
fopen(S);
```

```
while 1
```

```
% ReaDInGInpUt
```

```
out = get(S);
```

```
if out==1
```

```
fclose(S);
```

```
break;
```

```
end
```

```
end
```

****Image Acquisition****

```
% ImageAcquisition
```

```
Vin = videoinput('winvideo', 2);
```

```
% View properties of selected source
```

```
% Summary
```

```
% Src_Vin = getselectedsource(Vin);
```

```
% General settings
```

```
% get(Src_Vin);
```

```
% Preview image frames stream
```

```
preview(Vin);
```

```
% 3sec Delay
```

```
pause(3);
```

```
% Get single frame
```

```
frame = getsnapshot(Vin);
```

```
image(frame);
```

```
% Close video preview
```

```

closepreview(Vin)

% DelEteimAGefROmmemORy
%delete(Vin);

**Number Plate Extraction**

car1=frame;

% ManuAllYreADinGimAGe
%Car1=imread('.....\abc.jpg');

R=Car1(:,:,1); %REd
%figure, imshow(R)

G=Car1(:,:,2); %GreEN
%figure, imshow(G)

B=Car1(:,:,3); %BLuE
%figure, imshow(B)

% ExtRActiNGyeLlowcolOR
Car = (single(R) + single(G))/2 - single(B);
% TherSHold
Car = Car > 50;

```

```

% Clearborder
Car=imclearborder(Car,4);
%figure, imshow(Car)

% RemoveSmallObjects
Car=bwareaopen(Car,1000);
%figure, imshow(Car)

% Number of Objects and Labels
[Labels,NOD] = bwlabel(Car,8);

for loop = 1:1:NOD
    TT1(loop) = bwarea(find(Labels==loop));
end

% Extracting Found Labels

for loop = 1:1:NOD
    [R,C] = find(Labels==loop);
    %offset = 0;
    Rmin = min(R) %- offset;

```

```

Rmax = max(R) %+ offset;

Cmin = min(C) %- offset;

Cmax = max(C) %+ offset;

Carplate{loop} = imcrop(Car1,[CminRmin (Cmax-Cmin),(Rmax - Rmin)]);

%figure, imshow(Carplate{loop});

end

% SeleCtNumbErPlatE

for loop = 1:1:NOD

    a=size(Carplate{loop});

    if a<[50 100 4]

        Bulleyes=1;

        Carplate1=Carplate{loop};

        break;

    else

        Bulleyes=0;

    end

end

end

```

****Character Extraction****

```
CarplateG = rgb2gray(Carplate1);
```

```
%figure,imshow(CarplateG)
```

```
% Otsu's method
```

```
% figure,imhist(carplate)
```

```
level2 = graythresh(Carplate);
```

```
% BinARy
```

```
Carplate = im2bw(Carplate,level2);
```

```
% figure, imshow(Carplate);
```

```
% COmPLEmEnt
```

```
Carplate = imcomplement(Carplate);
```

```
% figure,imshow(Carplate)
```

```
% CleARborder
```

```
Carplate = imclearborder(Carplate, 8);
```

```
% figure, imshow(Carplate);
```

```

% ReMOviNgsmAlLObjEctS

Carplate = bwareaopen(Carplate,15);

% figure,imshow(Carplate)

% NumbEr of ObjEctsAnDlabEls

[labels,NOD] = bwlabel(Carplate,8);

% ExtrCtINgchAracTeRS

for loop = 1:1:NOD

[R,C] = find(labels==loop);

%offset = 0;

Rmin = min(R); %- offset;

Rmax = max(R); %+ offset;

Cmin = min(C); %- offset;

Cmax = max(C); %+ offset;

Numbers {loop} = imcrop(Carplate,[CminRmin (Cmax-Cmin),(Rmax - Rmin)]);

%figure, imshow(Numbers {loop})

NNumbers1 {loop}=imresize(Numbers {loop}, [42 24]);

NNumbers1 {loop} =~ NNumbers1 {loop};

%figure, imshow(NNumbers1 {loop});

end

```

****Character Images Load****

```
Characters=[];
```

```
Characters{1}=imread('0.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{1});
```

```
Characters{2}=imread('1.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{2});
```

```
Characters{3}=imread('2.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{3});
```

```
Characters{4}=imread('3.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{4});
```

```
Characters{5}=imread('4.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{5});
```

```
Characters{6}=imread('5.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{6});
```

```
Characters {7}=imread('6.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {7});
```

```
Characters {8}=imread('7.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {8});
```

```
Characters {9}=imread('8.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {9});
```

```
Characters {10}=imread('9.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {10});
```

```
Characters {11}=imread('A.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {11});
```

```
Characters {12}=imread('B.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {12});
```

```
Characters {13}=imread('C.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters {13});
```

```
Characters {14}=imread('D.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {14});  
  
Characters {15}=imread('E.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {15});  
  
Characters {16}=imread('F.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {16});  
  
Characters {17}=imread('G.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {17});  
  
Characters {18}=imread('H.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {18});  
  
Characters {19}=imread('I.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {19});  
  
Characters {20}=imread('J.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {20});  
  
Characters {21}=imread('K.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{21});
```

```
Characters{22}=imread('L.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{22});
```

```
Characters{23}=imread('M.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{23});
```

```
Characters{24}=imread('N.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{24});
```

```
Characters{25}=imread('O.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{25});
```

```
Characters{26}=imread('P.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{26});
```

```
Characters{27}=imread('Q.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{27});
```

```
Characters{28}=imread('R.bmp');
```

```
%figure, imshow(Characters{28});
```

```
Characters {29}=imread('S.bmp');  
  
%figure, imshow(Characters {29});  
  
Characters {30}=imread('T.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {30});  
  
Characters {31}=imread('U.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {31});  
  
Characters {32}=imread('V.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {32});  
  
Characters {33}=imread('W.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {33});  
  
Characters {34}=imread('X.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {34});  
  
Characters {35}=imread('Y.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters {35});
```

```
Characters{36}=imread('Z.bmp');  
%figure, imshow(Characters{36});
```

****Character Recognition****

```
word=[];
```

```
foraaaaa=1:NOD
```

```
imagn=NNumbers1 {aaaaa};
```

```
comp=[];
```

```
%imshow(templates{1,6})
```

```
for n=1:36
```

```
sem=corr2(Characters{1,n},imagn);
```

```
comp=[comp sem];
```

```
end
```

```
vd=find(comp==max(comp));
```

```
%CompAriNG
```

```
ifvd==1
```

```
letter='A';
```

```
elseifvd==2
```

```
letter='B';
```

```
elseifvd==3
```

```
letter='C';
```

```
elseifvd==4
```

```
letter='D';
```

```
elseifvd==5
```

```
letter='E';
```

```
elseifvd==6
```

```
letter='F';
```

```
elseifvd==7
```

```
letter='G';
```

```
elseifvd==8
```

```
letter='H';
```

```
elseifvd==9
```

```
letter='I';
```

```
elseifvd==10
```

```
letter='J';
```

```
elseifvd==11
```

```
letter='K';  
elseifvd==12  
letter='L';  
elseifvd==13  
letter='M';  
elseifvd==14  
letter='N';  
elseifvd==15  
letter='O';  
elseifvd==16  
letter='P';  
elseifvd==17  
letter='Q';  
elseifvd==18  
letter='R';  
elseifvd==19  
letter='S';  
elseifvd==20  
letter='T';  
elseifvd==21  
letter='U';  
elseifvd==22
```

```
letter='V';  
elseifvd==23  
letter='W';  
elseifvd==24  
letter='X';  
elseifvd==25  
letter='Y';  
elseifvd==26  
letter='Z';  
%*_*_*_*_*_*  
elseifvd==27  
letter='1';  
elseifvd==28  
letter='2';  
elseifvd==29  
letter='3';  
elseifvd==30  
letter='4';  
elseifvd==31  
letter='5';  
elseifvd==32  
letter='6';
```

```
elseif vd==33
```

```
letter='7';
```

```
elseif vd==34
```

```
letter='8';
```

```
elseif vd==35
```

```
letter='9';
```

```
elseif vd==36
```

```
letter='0';
```

```
end
```

```
for i=7:1:12
```

```
    a=cell2mat(Sheet1(i));
```

```
    s=isequal(word,a);
```

```
if s==1
```

```
    man=1;
```

```
break;
```

```
else
```

```
    man=0;
```

```
end
```

```
end
```

```

if man==1
msgbox(sprintf('StolenCarDetected..!! \n \n \" %s \" \n',word),'Extraction Success');
else
msgbox(sprintf('CarCleared..!! \n \n %s \n',word),'Extraction Success');
end

```

****Sending Message****

```

myaddress = 'fypscds10@gmail.com';
mypassword = 'jamarsh29';
setpref('Internet','E_mail',myaddress);
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Server','smtp.gmail.com');
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Username',myaddress);
setpref('Internet','SMTP_Password',mypassword);
props = java.lang.System.getProperties;
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.auth','true');
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.class', ...
'javax.net.ssl.SSLSocketFactory');
props.setProperty('mail.smtp.socketFactory.port','465');
sendmail(myaddress, 'Alert message', '%s This car is stolen.',word);
end

```

****Program Terminated****

Appendix C

Excel Datasheet

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
1	CIMG4143	ARF144																		
2	CIMG4153	CN9919																		
3	CIMG4181	AJL256																		
4	CIMG4183	AJM109																		
5	CIMG4206	AKA892																		
6	CIMG4208	AWS108																		
7																				
8																				
9																				
10																				
11																				
12																				
13																				
14																				
15																				
16																				
17																				
18																				
19																				
20																				
21																				
22																				
23																				
24																				

"In The Name Of ALLAH,

Most Gracious, Most Merciful."